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Growth Performance of Broiler Starter Chicks Fed Boiled Mango (*Mangifera Spp*) Kernel Composite Meal as A Replacement for Maize

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Abstract

A 28-day feeding trial was conducted to investigate the growth performance of SAYED broiler chicks fed varying levels of boiled mango composite meal (BMKCM). A total of 180 day-old chicks were randomly assigned to four dietary treatments, designated T₁- T₄, containing 0%, 10%, 15% and 20% inclusion levels of BMKCM respectively. Each treatment was replicated thrice with 15 chicks per replicate. Data were collected on growth indices and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using statistical package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 2010. The results showed no significant ($P>0.05$) differences across treatments in all the parameters measured. It was concluded that BMKCM could replace maize up to 20% in chicks' diets without depressive growth.

Keywords: Boiled mango kernel, maize, broiler chick, performance indices.

INTRODUCTION

Sources of conventional energy feedstuffs have become very expensive due to stiff competition between man, animals, and industries (Abang *et al.*, 2013; Gyang *et al.*, 2021; Ogana *et al.*, 2021). Consumption of animal sources of protein is on the decrease as a result of this; hike in operational cost; translated into high cost of animal's products like; meat, milk, eggs etc. Non-conventional energy feedstuffs that are less competed for are being sourced for (Ogana *et al.*, 2021, Abang *et al.*, 2023a &b). Mango seed kernel (MSK) is reported to be a good source of carbohydrates (NFE) (Abang *et al.*, 2015, 2017, 2018; Diarra and Usman, 2008; Diarra *et al.*, 2010; 2011), and contains high quantities of proteins and fats (Abang *et al.*, 2016). Although there are reports of the consumption of MSK as porridge in India (El Saadany *et al.*, 1980; Opeke, 1982); this by-product has limited food, feed or industrial uses in most mango producing countries thus making it readily available. The major problem affecting the nutritional value of MSK is that it contains various anti nutritional factors (tannins, phytates, oxalates). Processing methods such as; fermentation, boiling, sun-drying etc. have been used to bring the levels of anti- nutrients to a more tolerable state (Abang *et al.*, 2013a&b). MSK meal has received much

June 30, 2023

research attention in recent years as an alternate energy source for poultry. This paper seeks to investigate effect of graded levels of boiled mango kernel composite meal on the growth performance of broiler chicks.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site

This experiment was conducted at the poultry unit of the Teaching and Research Farm of the Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State. Makurdi is located in the middle belt region of Nigeria. Its geographic coordinates are latitude 7^o44 North, longitude 8^o32 East and has 104 metres elevation above the sea level. It has mean rainfall of 1259-2000mm and mean annual temperature range of 23^oC to 32^oC. The rainy period is between April to October and dry period from November to March. Many cultivars of both indigenous and improved mango are produced in large quantities in the area with the peak production in April to May. During this period, mango seed (containing the kernel) poses a serious environmental problem because it has no food, feed or industrial use in the area

Preparation of experimental materials

Mango seeds were collected during the month of May-August in Gboko, Buruku and Makurdi areas of Benue State, Nigeria. Mango kernel was removed by cracking manually with the aid of hammer. The kernel seed were boiled in already 100^oc water for at least 20 minutes afterwards, it was sun-dried for 168 hours (7 days) in order to reduce the moisture content to less than 10% for prolonged storage. Soybean was well toasted to a dark brown colour to reduce the level of anti- nutrients such as tannin, oxalate, trypsin inhibitors, saponin, phytate, flavonoid, cyanides etc. The ingredients were crushed separately into fine grit (maize and soybean) and were later mixed at varying inclusion levels with other ingredients to formulate the various diets.

Experimental diet

The various diets were formulated to meet the nutritive requirements for broiler chickens. Boiled mango kernel composite meal was used to replace maize at 0%, 10%, 15% and 20%. (Table 4).

Experimental animal and housing

One hundred and eighty (180) broiler chicks of different weight were obtained from SAYED farm in Ibadan Nigeria and randomly assigned to four treatments (T₁, T₂, T₃ and T₄) in a completely randomized design. Each treatment consisting of forty-five (45) birds and was replicated into three (3) with 15 birds each per replicate. The house was half-walled, roofed with zinc coated metal sheets. The birds were managed intensively in cages of three tiers. Each tier was separated with wood. Wire mesh was used for the walls and doors to allow adequate ventilation/lighting. The dimension of each tier was (1.0 m² X 0.78 m²). Litter materials (wood shavings) were used on the wooden floors. Each tier was equipped with adequate drinkers and feeding troughs. A floor space of about 0.007m² to 0.009m² per bird was provided. Source of lighting was provided with the use of electric bulbs to ensure adequate feed intake and local (Abacha) stove as source of heat. Conventional management practices were adopted.

Experimental procedures and data collection

The initial body weights of birds were taken and the birds were randomly distributed into the various experimental units. A known quantity of diets was served to the birds and left over weighed. Feed and drinking

June 30, 2023

water were given separate *ad libitum* throughout the period of experiment which lasted for eight (8) weeks. Mean daily feed consumption and weekly weight gain were determined. Parameters measured were feed intake, body weight and feed conversion ratio. Initial live weight was determined by weighing the birds averagely per replicate. The feed intake was determined by serving known weight of feed and weighing of leftover feed, calculating the difference between the feed supplied and the feed leftover. The weight gain was also determined by subtracting the initial weight from the final weight.

Formulae;

Feed intake = feed served – leftover feed.

Weight gain = Body weight of the current week minus the weight of the previous week. I.e, week 2 weight – week 1

Feed conversion = feed intake/ weight gain, that is feed intake divided by weight gain.

Body weight = Average weekly weight of chicks.

Table 3: Composition of starter broiler diet with boiled mango kernel composite meal .

Ingredient(kg)	Inclusion level %			
	0%	10%	15%	20%
Maize	54.00	48.60	45.90	43.20
BMKCM	0.00	5.40	8.10	10.80
Soybean meal	32.98	34.00	34.00	34.00
BDG	5.50	4.26	4.26	4.26
Blood meal	2.97	3.00	3.00	3.14
Bone meal	3.50	3.74	3.74	3.60
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Lysine	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Analyzed nutrients:

M.E (kcal/kg)	2760.30	2792.02	2807.49	2823.63
Crude protein	23.14	24.48	23.40	23.43
Lysine	1.32	1.32	1.31	1.32
Methionine	0.61	0.61	0.60	0.62
Ether extract	3.94	3.19	4.35	4.50
Crude fibre	4.54	4.40	4.73	4.37
Calcium	1.40	1.48	1.48	1.43
Phosphorus	0.80	0.82	0.82	0.80

BMKCM=Boiled Mango Kernel Meal, BDG=Brewer's Dry Grain, T₁(0%), T₂ (10%), T₃(15%) and T₄ (20%)

Chemical analysis

Processed boiled mango kernel composite meal was analyzed for proximate fractions according to the methods described by AOAC (2006).

June 30, 2023

Statistical analysis

The data collected on all the parameters studied were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Minitab software version 14 (Minitab, 2004) and least significant method (LSD) was used to separate means that differed significantly (P,0.05) according to Steel and Torrie (1980).

Results and Discussion

Proximate composition of boiled mango (*mangifera spp*) kernel meal

Proximate analysis of boiled mango kernel composite meal (BMKCM) is presented in Table 2. The results for the Proximate fractions were: 5.25%, 1.32%, 9.33%, 2.17%, 11.33% and 70.60% for CP (crude protein), CF (crude fibre), EE (ether extracts), ash, moisture and NFE (nitrogen free extract) respectively. The result for CP revealed that the CP (5.25%) for this current work was lower than the reports of Abang *et al*; 2016 and Abang *et al*; 2017 who recorded a CP of 7.00% and 11.38% with SMK (sun dried mango kernel meal) and FMKCM (fermented mango kernel composite meal) respectively. The CP recorded by Abang *et al*; 2016 and Abang *et al*; 2017 were higher probably as a result of the different processing methods employed. Heat is said to denature protein, this could have accounted for the lower value of CP for BMKCM. Diarra *et al*; 2010, also recorded values for both raw mango kernel and boiled mango kernel which are both higher than the result from the current study (8.70 and 8.63% respectively). This may be as a result of different processing method and varietal differences.

The result of CF (1.32%) was lower than the values reported by Elegbede *et al*; 1995 who worked on raw mango kernel (CF 2.5%). The processing method (boiling) might have accounted for this reduction. Diarra *et al*., 2011 who worked on both raw and boiled mango kernel recorded values which are slightly lower than the result from the current study (1.11 and 1.23% respectively). This tally with Abang *et al*. (2017) recorded a CF of (1.49%) with FMKCM. This appears to be higher than the values recorded in this present study probably because of the less fibrous mango kernels that dominated the composite as there are varietal differences in the chemical composition of the composite mango kernel. Also, fermentation process has been known for efficient reduction of fibre as the fungi (yeast) responsible for fermentation release enzymes that react on the cellulose (fibre). Diarra *et al*., 2010 also recorded values which are higher than that of the current study for both raw and boiled mango kernel (2.02 and 2.10 respectively).

The result for fats and oil (EE) was 9.33%. The result was lower than those reported by Elegbede *et al*. (1995) and Abang *et al*. (2017) who worked on raw mango kernel and fermented mango kernel composite meal respectively. This could be as a result of the boiling which might have leached away the fats and oil. Diarra *et al*., 2011 recorded values for both raw and boiled mango kernel (7.87 and 9.22% respectively). This result by Diarra *et al*., 2011 in comparison to the current study shows that differences in processing methods affect the availability of fats in the mango kernel.

The result of ash (mineral and vitamin) was 2.17%. The result was a bit higher than those reported by Abang *et al*; 2016 (ash 2.00%) and Abang *et al*; 2017 (ash 0.86%) who worked on SMK and FMKCM respectively. This could be as a result of varietal difference in chemical composition of the used mango kernel and used. Diarra *et al*; 2011 also recorded results which are lower than that of the current study (0.45 and 0.29% for both raw and boiled mango kernel respectively). This is attributed to differences in methods of processing and varietal difference. Meanwhile, Diarra *et al*; 2010 recorded values for both raw and boiled mango kernel (6.04 and 5.96% respectively), this vividly shows the roles of processing methods as well as varietal differences.

June 30, 2023

The result of moisture was 11.33%. This was higher than the results reported by Abang *et al.*, 2016 (5.16%) and Abang *et al.*; 2017 (8.64%) who worked with SMK and FMKCM respectively. This is probably as a result of the increased surface area of contact with the boiling water in which the kernels absorbed during boiling.

The result for nitrogen free extract (NFE) was 70.60%. The result was lower than the 78.59% reported by Abang *et al.*; 2016 for sun dried mango kernel meal but higher than the 61.46% reported by Abang *et al.*; 2017 for fermented mango kernel composite meal, probably because of the different processing methods, and the varietal chemical composition differences. Diarra *et al.*; 2011 recorded an even higher result for both raw and boiled mango kernel (82.56 and 81.54% respectively. Diarra *et al.*; 2010 meanwhile recorded similar result to the current study for both raw and boiled mango kernel (70.23 and 69.93% respectively).

Table 2:- Proximate Composition of Boiled Mango (*Mangifera Spp*) Kernel Meal.

Components	Percentage (%)
Moisture	11.33
Crude protein	5.25
Crude fibre	1.32
Ether extract	9.33
Ash	2.17

Mean weekly feed intake of broiler chicks fed boiled mango kernel composite meal ranged from 105.17±21.51-107.46±35.92g. Result revealed that feed intake showed no significant ($P>0.005$) difference across the treatments. This observation was different from that of Abang *et al.* (2017) when varying levels of fermented mango kernel composite meal (FMKCM) was served to broiler Chicks, this may be as a result of differences in processing methods. The result (66.3-70.8g) recorded by Yibrehu *et al.*, 2012 who used mango fruit waste in broiler chicken diet contradicts this report. Diarra *et al.* (2011) also has different result on the use of boiled mango kernel meal in broiler diet; this could be attributed to varietal differences. The mean body weight ranged from 288.26±62.60g - 317.57±71.73g. The non-significant effect on the mean body weight indicates that the diets were adequately utilized by the chicks probably because of the processing method employed, as boiling enhances nutrients; vitamins and essential amino acid by improving protein and fibre digestibility. This result was similar to the report of Abang *et al.* (2017) who observed no significant ($P>0.005$) differences in body weight of broiler chicks fed varying levels of FMKCM. There was no depressive growth recorded, implying that boiling of the mango kernel reduced the anti-nutritional factors like tannins and protein inhibitors (trypsin and chymotrypsin), as tannins form complexes with protein and limit their availability to a tolerable level. The mean weight gain which ranged from 89.34±16.13g – 102.04±15.87g was not significant ($P>0.05$) across treatment groups. This confirms the reports of Diarra *et al.*(2011) who observed a non-significant ($P>0.05$) effect with the use of boiled in broiler's diet and Orayaga *et al.*(2017), who used composite mango fruit reject meal in broiler chicks; but was in contrast with the assertions of Abang *et al.* (2017) who fed broiler chicks with FMKCM. These differences in results may be due to differences in methods of processing. Diarra and Usman (2008) reported depressive growth for broiler chicks fed varying levels of mango kernel meal, probably due to the anti-nutritional factors (tannins and trypsin) present which limits the availability of protein to the birds. The mean feed conversion ratio (FCR) of broiler chicks fed varying levels of boiled mango kernel composite meal ranged from 1.10±0.35 - 1.39±0.48 and was lower and better than that reported (2.47-3.45) by Diarra *et al.*(2011) and Abang *et al.* (2017) (3.84-4.58) for broiler chicks fed boiled mango kernel meal and fermented mango kernel meal, respectively. A better FCR recorded in this study may be due to varietal differences. .

Table 3: Summarized Table of Performance characteristics of Broiler Chicks Fed Varying Level of Boiled Mango Kernel Meal (g).

June 30, 2023

Parameters	0%	10%	15%	20%
AWFI	107.46±15.70	105.82±35.92	106.89±26.80	105.17±21.51
AWBW	317.57±71.73	291.59±64.43	291.35±63.43	288.26±62.60
AWWG	102.04±15.87	93.03±17.28	92.12±15.02	89.34±16.13
EFU	1.10±0.35	1.35±0.48	1.29±0.36	1.39±0.48

AWFI=Average weekly feed intake, AWBW=Average weekly body weight, AWWG=Average weekly weight gain, EFU=Efficiency of feed utilization.

Conclusion

The study concluded that BMKCM is a good alternative source of energy and could replace maize up to 20% in starter broiler diet without depressive growth.

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June 30, 2023

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